

Optimization of Thermal Conductivity of Handloom Woven Silk–Cotton Union Fabrics using Response Surface Methodology

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Abstract:

Thermal conductivity is a key determinant of thermos-physiological comfort in apparel textiles, governing the rate of heat transfer between the human body and the external environment. Although pure silk (silk-by-silk) fabrics are widely appreciated for their lusture, drape, and smooth handle, previous studies report relatively higher thermal conductivity due to the compact filament structure and reduced air entrapment, which may limit insulation performance under variable climatic conditions. Earlier investigations have concentrated on mechanized woven systems or single-fiber constructions, with limited systematic optimization of handloom-woven silk–cotton union fabrics using statistical design approaches. Addressing this research gap, the present study employed Response Surface Methodology based on a Box–Behnken Design to optimize thermal conductivity by varying weft yarn count (20–40 Ne), twist per inch (10–20 TPI), and picks per inch (55–65 PPI), while maintaining constant silk warp parameters. Thermal conductivity ranged from 0.0014 to 0.0020 W/m·K, with pick density showing the most significant influence; the minimum value (≈ 0.0014 W/m·K) was achieved at moderate yarn fineness, controlled twist, and higher pick density. Compared with silk-by-silk fabrics, the optimized union fabrics exhibited lower thermal conductivity due to enhanced air entrapment from cotton weft yarns. The study demonstrates the potential of statistically engineered handloom fabrics for sustainable, climate-responsive apparel, with future prospects in smart textile integration and performance-oriented garment design.

Keywords : Box–Behnken Design, Handloom fabrics, Response Surface Methodology, Silk–Cotton union fabrics, Thermal conductivity, Weft yarn count

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1. Introduction

Thermal comfort is a critical performance requirement in apparel textiles, as it directly influences heat regulation, wearer satisfaction, and physiological balance. Among thermo-physical properties, thermal conductivity (W/m·K) is a key parameter that governs the rate of heat transfer through textile materials. It determines whether a fabric allows rapid heat dissipation, creating a cooling sensation in warm climates, or restricts heat flow, providing insulation under cooler conditions [1, 2]. Because textiles are porous assemblies of fibers and entrapped air, their effective thermal conductivity depends not only on the intrinsic conductivity of fibers but also on structural parameters such as yarn count, yarn twist, fabric density, thickness, and porosity. Since still air has a very low thermal conductivity (~ 0.024 W/m·K), the amount and distribution of air within the fabric structure significantly influence overall heat transfer behavior [3].

Previous research has demonstrated that fabric geometry plays a decisive role in thermal performance [2] reported that increased fabric thickness enhances thermal resistance due to greater air entrapment, thereby lowering effective heat conduction. Similarly, [4] investigated knitted cotton fabrics

and observed thermal conductivity values in the range of 0.072–0.082 W/m·K, confirming that structural compactness and fabric density significantly influence conductive heat transfer [5] further demonstrated that structural modifications that increase air pockets within fabric assemblies improve insulation by reducing effective thermal conductivity. These findings collectively highlight that thermal conductivity is not merely fiber-dependent but strongly governed by structural engineering and yarn configuration [6].

Natural fibers such as silk and cotton exhibit distinct thermal behaviors due to differences in their morphology and molecular structure. Cotton, a cellulosic staple fiber, possesses moderate intrinsic thermal conductivity and a bulky yarn structure that promotes air entrapment within woven assemblies [7]. In contrast, silk is a continuous filament protein fiber characterized by a smooth surface, compact structure, and high tensile strength (up to 500 MPa) [8, 9]. Pure silk (silk-by-silk) fabrics typically exhibit more compact filament alignment, which can influence heat transfer pathways differently compared to staple fiber-based fabrics. Silk–cotton union fabrics combine the complementary characteristics of these two natural fibers within a single woven structure. In such constructions, silk warp yarns provide dimensional stability, strength, and

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aesthetic luster, while cotton weft yarns introduce bulkiness and structural openness. The interaction between silk's relatively compact filament arrangement and cotton's air-trapping staple yarn structure may significantly affect the overall thermal conductivity of the fabric. However, despite the functional importance of such hybrid textiles, limited research has focused on systematically optimizing the thermal conductivity of handloom-woven silk-cotton union fabrics [10-13].

Handloom weaving represents a sustainable and culturally significant segment of the textile industry, particularly in developing economies. Compared to mechanized weaving, handloom production consumes less energy and allows precise control over yarn insertion, tension, and pick density [14, 15]. These controllable parameters such as weft yarn count, twist per inch (TPI), and picks per inch (PPI), which directly influence fabric compactness, porosity, and thickness, and therefore play a vital role in determining thermal conductivity. However, the absence of systematic scientific optimization has limited the performance enhancement and standardization of handloom union fabrics [10-13]. To address this research gap, advanced statistical tools such as Response Surface Methodology (RSM) have been effectively applied in textile engineering for modeling and optimizing multi-variable systems [16-19]. The Box-Behnken Design (BBD), a class of RSM, enables efficient evaluation of three independent variables and their interaction effects with a reduced number of experimental runs [20, 18]. This approach facilitates the development of predictive mathematical models and identification of optimal structural configurations for desired thermal performance.

Therefore, the present study aims to optimize the thermal conductivity of handloom-woven silk-cotton union fabrics using Response Surface Methodology. By systematically varying cotton weft yarn count, twist per inch, and picks per

inch while maintaining constant silk warp parameters, this research seeks to develop a statistically validated predictive model and determine the optimal structural combination that minimizes thermal conductivity. The novelty of this work lies in integrating traditional handloom craftsmanship with modern statistical optimization techniques to engineer thermally efficient, sustainable hybrid fabrics suitable for diverse climatic applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials Used

In the present study, yarn materials and structural parameters were systematically selected to investigate the effect of fabric construction on the thermal conductivity of handloom-woven silk-cotton Union fabrics using Response Surface Methodology based on the Box-Behnken Design. Three independent variables were considered for optimization: cotton weft yarn linear density (A), twist per inch of the weft yarn (B), and picks per inch (C). These parameters were selected because they directly govern yarn packing density, fabric compactness, thickness, porosity, and the volume of entrapped air within the fabric structure, which collectively control conductive heat transfer in woven textiles [10-13].

Fabric samples were prepared on a traditional handloom under controlled conditions to ensure uniformity. A constant warp of 253 Ne silk was maintained at 96 ends per inch for all samples. The weft consisted of 100% cotton yarns with linear densities of 20, 30, and 40 Ne, further the fabric construction parameters and twist per inch were varied systematically by adjusting picks per inch 55, 60, & 65 and TPI 10, 15 & 20 respectively, as presented in Table 1. All samples were woven in plain weave structure to maintain consistency, enabling a systematic assessment of the influence of weft variables on the resulting fabric properties.

Table 1 - Structural Parameters and Estimated Physical Properties of Handloom Woven Silk-Cotton Union Fabrics

Sample Id	Weft Yarn Linear Density (Ne)	Ends per Inch (EPI)	Picks per Inch (PPI)	Twist per Inch (TPI)	Fabric Mass (GSM) (g/m ²)	Thickness (mm)	Air Permeability (cm ³ /cm ² /s)
S1	20	96	55	15	121	0.36	162.32
S2	40	96	55	15	95	0.28	176.38
S3	20	96	65	15	132	0.39	120.83
S4	40	96	65	15	104	0.31	152.86
S5	20	96	60	10	123	0.35	138.81
S6	40	96	60	10	99	0.29	159.84
S7	20	96	60	20	125	0.37	143.26
S8	40	96	60	20	101	0.30	165.39
S9	30	96	55	10	105	0.31	164.89
S10	30	96	65	10	114	0.33	133.66
S11	30	96	55	20	107	0.32	168.64
S12	30	96	65	20	116	0.34	130.91
S13	30	96	60	15	112	0.33	158.98
S14	30	96	60	15	112	0.33	157.72
S15	30	96	60	15	112	0.33	151.85

2.2 Fabric Construction Process

All fabric samples were produced on a traditional handloom to maintain low yarn tension and precise control of structural parameters. Handloom weaving is also considered an energy-efficient and environmentally sustainable method compared to mechanized systems. A plain weave structure was used for all samples to ensure uniform yarn interlacement and minimize the influence of weave geometry, enabling evaluation of yarn count, twist per inch, and pick density on thermal conductivity. Warp preparation was carried out using a peg warping system. Fabrics were woven following a three-factor, three-level Box–Behnken design, producing 15 samples (S1–S15). After scouring and air drying, samples were conditioned at 20 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 2 % RH for 24 h before testing.

2.3 Experimental Design Using Box–Behnken Design

To systematically investigate the influence of yarn and fabric structural parameters on the thermal conductivity of silk–cotton Union fabrics, a three-factor, three-level Box–Behnken Design was employed within the Response Surface Methodology framework. The Box–Behnken Design was selected because it efficiently estimates second-order polynomial models and interaction effects using a reduced number of experimental runs, thereby minimizing material consumption and experimental effort while maintaining adequate statistical reliability, as widely reported in optimization studies on textile materials [17, 18 & 20]. In comparison to Central Composite Design, which requires a larger number of experiments and axial points, the Box–Behnken Design provides comparable predictive capability with fewer experimental combinations, making it particularly suitable for optimization studies involving handloom-woven fabrics where large-scale experimentation is constrained [21, 22].

In the present study, three independent variables were selected based on their direct influence on fabric compactness, thickness, and internal air entrapment, which govern conductive heat transfer in woven textiles. These variables were weft yarn count (Ne, factor A), twist per inch of the weft yarn (TPI, factor B), and picks per inch (PPI, factor C). Each variable was studied at three coded levels (-1, 0, and +1), corresponding to low, medium, and high values, respectively, as summarized in Table 2. The experimental design generated fifteen fabric combinations (S1–S15), forming a balanced and nearly rotatable design suitable for modeling and optimization of thermal conductivity. Experimental data were analyzed using quadratic polynomial regression, and Design-Expert software. The general regression model is expressed as:

$$Y = B_0 + \sum B_i X_i + \sum B_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \sum B_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (1)$$

Where Y represents thermal conductivity (W/m·K), B_0 is the intercept, B_i denotes linear coefficients, B_{ii} represents quadratic coefficients, and B_{ij} indicates interaction effects of the coded variables A, B, and C.

Table 2 - Coded and actual levels of independent variables

Factor	Symbol	Level -1	Level 0	Level +1
Weft Yarn Count (Ne)	A	20	30	40
Twist per Inch (TPI)	B	10	15	20
Picks per Inch (PPI)	C	55	60	65

The actual and predicted values of thermal conductivity obtained from the 15 experimental runs are presented in Table 3. The close agreement between experimental and predicted values confirms the suitability of the quadratic model for capturing the influence of yarn fineness, twist, and pick density on the thermal behavior of the fabric. Thermal conductivity values ranged from 0.0014 to 0.002 W/m·K across different sample combinations, demonstrating the sensitivity of heat transfer characteristics to structural variations in the fabric.

Table 3 - Experimental and predicted responses of silk–cotton union fabrics

Sample Id	Independent variables			Thermal conductivity Watt/ m. K	
	Ne (A)	PPI (B)	TPI (C)	Actual Value	Predicted Value
S1	20	65	15	0.0015	0.0015
S2	30	65	20	0.0016	0.0016
S3	20	55	15	0.0018	0.0018
S4	30	60	15	0.0014	0.0015
S5	40	65	15	0.0016	0.0016
S6	30	65	10	0.0014	0.0015
S7	40	60	20	0.0018	0.0018
S8	30	55	20	0.0019	0.0019
S9	40	60	10	0.0016	0.0016
S10	20	60	10	0.0016	0.0015
S11	40	55	15	0.002	0.002
S12	20	60	20	0.0015	0.0016
S13	30	55	10	0.0018	0.0018
S14	30	60	15	0.0015	0.0015
S15	30	60	15	0.0016	0.0015

3. Measurement of Fabric Properties

3.1 Thermal Conductivity

Thermal conductivity of the handloom-woven silk–cotton union fabric samples was measured using the Lee's Disc Method in accordance with ASTM D1518. Prior to testing, the instrument was calibrated to ensure accurate steady-state heat transfer measurements. Fabric specimens of 10 cm × 10 cm were conditioned under standard atmospheric conditions and placed between the heated and lower disc assemblies.

After attaining thermal equilibrium, the temperature difference was recorded and thermal conductivity (W/m·K) was calculated using Fourier's law of heat conduction. Thermal conductivity indicates the ability of a fabric to transfer heat. Lower values correspond to better insulation performance, while moderate values promote controlled heat dissipation, contributing to balanced thermal comfort [1].

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Analysis of Variance

Thermal conductivity (TC) of the developed silk–cotton union fabrics was analyzed using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) based on a Box–Behnken Design comprising seventeen experimental runs. The effects of weft yarn count (A), picks per inch (B), and twist per inch (C) were evaluated using ANOVA (Table 4) to develop a quadratic regression model. The statistical model was found to be significant (F = 11.20, p = 0.008), with a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.9527 and adjusted R² of 0.8676, indicating that over 95% of the variation in thermal conductivity is explained by the selected parameters. The lack-of-fit was not significant, confirming the adequacy of the model.

Among the linear factors, picks per inch (B) showed the most significant negative influence (−0.0002), indicating that fabric density strongly governs thermal behavior. The quadratic term B² was also statistically significant (F = 20.42, p = 0.0063), demonstrating a non-linear relationship between fabric density and heat transfer. The interaction terms (AB, AC, and BC) were statistically insignificant within the studied range.

The developed second-order polynomial equation for thermal conductivity is:

$$TC = 0.0015 + 0.0001A - 0.0002B + 0.0001C - 0.0000AB + 0.0001AC + 0.0000BC + 0.0001A^2 + 0.0002B^2 + 0.0000C^2 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Overall, the results indicate that picks per inch is the dominant factor influencing thermal conductivity, with a significant quadratic effect highlighting non-linear heat transfer behavior. The high R² value confirms the robustness of the model for predicting and optimizing thermal conductivity in handloom silk–cotton union fabrics as shown in Fig.2.

Figure 1 - Plot of predicted versus actual values (a) and Normal Probability Plot versus Externally Studentized residuals (b) of Thermal Conductivity (TC, in W/m·K)

Table 4 - ANOVA for Thermal Conductivity (TC, in W/m·K)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	4.401E-07	9	4.890E-08	11.20	0.0080	significant
A-Weft Count	4.961E-08	1	4.961E-08	11.36	0.0199	
B-Picks Per Inch	2.245E-07	1	2.245E-07	51.38	0.0008	
C-Twist Per Inch	4.061E-08	1	4.061E-08	9.30	0.0285	
AB	1.600E-09	1	1.600E-09	0.3663	0.5715	
AC	1.823E-08	1	1.823E-08	4.17	0.0966	
BC	9.000E-10	1	9.000E-10	0.2060	0.6689	
A ²	1.963E-08	1	1.963E-08	4.49	0.0875	
B ²	8.919E-08	1	8.919E-08	20.42	0.0063	
C ²	5.308E-09	1	5.308E-09	1.22	0.3205	
Residual	2.184E-08	5	4.368E-09			
Lack of Fit	1.575E-09	3	5.250E-10	0.0518	0.9806	not significant
Pure Error	2.027E-08	2	1.013E-08			
Cor Total	4.620E-07	14				
Std. Dev.	0.0001	R²			0.9527	
Mean	0.0017	Adjusted R²			0.8676	
C.V. %	3.98	Predicted R²			0.8467	

4.2 Impact of Weft Count (A), Picks per Inch (B), and Twist per Inch (C) on Thermal Conductivity (TC)

The combined influence of weft count (Ne), picks per inch (PPI), and twist per inch (TPI) on thermal conductivity (TC, W/m·K) is illustrated in Fig. 2. The response surface and contour plots demonstrate the interaction between two variables at a time while keeping the third parameter constant, thereby clarifying the structural factors governing conductive heat transfer in the woven silk–cotton union fabrics.

As shown in Fig. 2a and 2b, the interaction between PPI and weft count reveals a gradual increase in TC from approximately 0.00145 W/m·K at lower Ne (~20) and PPI (~55) to nearly 0.0020 W/m·K at higher Ne (~40) and PPI (~65). Coarser yarns combined with lower pick density create a more porous structure with higher air entrapment, resulting in lower effective thermal conductivity. In contrast, finer yarns and increased pick density reduce porosity and enhance fiber contact, thereby facilitating conductive heat transfer.

The interaction between TPI and weft count is presented in Fig. 2c and 2d. A non-linear relationship is observed, with minimum TC (~0.0015 W/m·K) occurring at intermediate weft counts (~30–35 Ne) and moderate twist levels (~14–16 TPI). At lower twist levels, yarns may exhibit higher internal porosity, while excessive twist increases compactness and restricts effective inter-yarn heat pathways. Moderate twist therefore appears to optimize fiber packing and alignment, resulting in balanced heat transfer. The influence of yarn twist on thermal behavior through structural compactness has been widely documented.

Figure 2 - Interaction between PPI and weft count: (a) surface plot and (b) contour plot; the interaction between TPI and weft count: (c) surface plot and (d) contour plot; and the interaction between TPI and PPI: (e) surface plot and (f) contour plot

The interaction between TPI and PPI is shown in Fig. 2e and 2f. Thermal conductivity decreases with increasing PPI at lower twist levels, reaching minimum values (~0.0014 W/m·K) in relatively dense fabrics formed with low-to-moderate twist yarns. However, at higher TPI (~20), TC remains comparatively elevated despite increased pick density, suggesting that excessive yarn compactness limits effective inter-yarn thermal pathways. The contour plot confirms that maximum TC occurs at low PPI combined with high TPI, while minimum TC is achieved at higher PPI and moderate TPI. This highlights the dominant role of structural density and inter-yarn connectivity in governing heat conduction. Overall, the results presented in Fig. 2a to 2f demonstrate that thermal conductivity is controlled by the coupled and non-linear interactions of yarn fineness, fabric density, and yarn twist. Higher TC is associated with finer yarns, increased pick density, and higher twist, whereas lower TC is achieved with coarser yarns, moderate density, and controlled twist. These findings provide a scientific basis for optimizing weaving parameters to tailor thermal performance in handloom-woven silk–cotton union fabrics.

5. Conclusion

This study successfully optimized the thermal conductivity of handloom-woven silk–cotton union fabrics using Response Surface Methodology based on a Box–Behnken

Design, developing a statistically significant quadratic regression model ($F = 11.20$, $p = 0.008$) with high predictive accuracy ($R^2 = 0.9527$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.8676$). The results identified picks per inch (PPI) as the most influential parameter, showing a significant negative linear and quadratic effect on thermal conductivity, confirming the non-linear relationship between fabric density and heat transfer. Thermal conductivity ranged from approximately 0.0014 to 0.0020 W/m·K, with lower values achieved at moderate twist (~15 TPI), optimized PPI, and relatively coarser weft yarns, which enhanced air entrapment and reduced conductive pathways. Compared to silk-by-silk fabrics, which typically exhibit compact filament alignment and more continuous heat conduction, the silk–cotton union structure demonstrated improved thermal regulation due to the bulkier cotton weft modifying structural porosity and heat transfer mechanisms. This highlights the advantage of union fabrics in achieving balanced thermal comfort while retaining silk's strength and aesthetic appeal. The developed model provides a reliable predictive tool for engineering thermally efficient handloom fabrics, supporting performance enhancement, product standardization, and sustainable value addition in the traditional textile sector, with future scope for multi-response optimization and advanced eco-friendly finishing applications.

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